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ABCD3 functions in multi-drug resistance in human cancer.

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We describe here a function for the ATP-binding cassette gene *ABCD3* in multi-drug resistance in human cancer (1-3), supported by evidence by demonstrating its transcriptional up-regulation with significance at the transcriptome level in metastasis to distant organ sites in human breast cancer (4, 5), and by separate evidence demonstrating that ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance: in resistance to a platinum agent, in resistance to doxorubicin, and in resistance to paclitaxel (2).

Results

Figure 1: ABCD3 is differentially expressed in the lung metastases of humans with breast cancer.

I. Metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumor of the breast (human)

n=2 metastasis to the lung (human)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
5825	9.86E-02	0.71	-1.651725	-1.1732438	1836.41	ABCD3	5367/22997	76.7

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors in humans with breast cancer and metastasis to the lung, we discovered differential expression of ATP binding cassette subfamily D member 3, encoded by *ABCD3* in metastasis to the lung in breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *ABCD3* changed more than 75% of the human breast cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *ABCD3* messenger RNA in breast cancer lung metastasis, demonstrating up-regulation of *ABCD3* during disease progression and metastasis.

II. Metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumor of the breast (human)

n=6 metastasis to the lung (human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100309262_TGI_at	1.02E-01	-1.71	-4.2229	-0.4623219	ABCD3	3406/52378	93.5

Through comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with breast cancer as compared to metastasis to the lung, we validated differential expression and transcriptional induction of *ABCD3* in lung metastasis in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of *ABCD3* here changed more than 90% of the breast cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 52,378 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *ABCD3* messenger RNA in the lung metastases of humans with breast cancer, demonstrating up-regulation of *ABCD3* during transformation and disease progression.

Thus, differential and increased expression of *ABCD3* defines the lung metastatic tumor transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

We described here transcriptional induction of a gene with functions in multi-drug resistance, in lung metastasis in human breast cancer. Novel approaches to challenging metastasis and resistance will utilize chemotherapy in conjunction with i) kinase and phosphatase inhibitors targeted to tissue and tumor type whose functions overlap with that of growth factor and growth factor receptor inhibitors, ii) inhibitors of the ATP-binding cassette family (multi-drug resistance pumps), and iii) CDK4/6 inhibitors, which function as senescence-inducing agents.

1 **References**

- 2 1. Gottesman, M.M., Fojo, T. and Bates, S.E., 2002. Multidrug resistance in cancer: role of
3 ATP-dependent transporters. *Nature reviews cancer*, 2(1), pp.48-58.
- 4 2. Mamoor, S. 2025. ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance in human cancer.
- 5 3. Robey, R.W., Pluchino, K.M., Hall, M.D., Fojo, A.T., Bates, S.E. and Gottesman, M.M., 2018.
6 Revisiting the role of ABC transporters in multidrug-resistant cancer. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 18(7),
pp.452-464.
- 7 4. GSE191230: Ong, L.T., Lee, W.C., Ma, S., Oguz, G., Niu, Z., Bao, Y., Yusuf, M., Lee, P.L., Goh,
8 J.Y., Wang, P. and Yong, K.S.M., 2022. IFI16-dependent STING signaling is a crucial regulator of
anti-HER2 immune response in HER2+ breast cancer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*,
119(31), p.e2201376119.
- 9 5. GSE56493: Tobin, N.P., Harrell, J.C., Lövrot, J., Brage, S.E., Stolt, M.F., Carlsson, L., Einbeigi, Z.,
10 Linderholm, B., Loman, N., Malmberg, M. and Walz, T., 2015. Molecular subtype and tumor characteristics
of breast cancer metastases as assessed by gene expression significantly influence patient post-relapse
11 survival. *Annals of oncology*, 26(1), pp.81-88.
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Methods

We measured total transcription in primary tumors and metastasis to distant organ sites including the bones, the brain, the liver and the lungs using microarray and RNA-sequencing datasets (GSEXXXXX and GSEXXXXX) and R-based computational software for exact quantitative determination of multi-drug resistant pump transcriptional induction at the transcriptome level.